

Do countries with similar environmental impact share values? An integrated analysis to inform environmental education

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ABSTRACT

Understanding which values associate with sustainable outcomes is essential for rethinking environmental education (EE). This study investigates whether countries with high human development but low environmental impact share distinctive value patterns that could inform EE frameworks. Using an integrative approach, we combined data from two sustainability databases –the Global Footprint Network and the Sustainable Development Index– with the European Values Study/World Values Survey (2017–2022). A total of 591 categorical variables were analysed using Cramér's V to identify significant differences between low, medium, and high environmental impact country groups, selected among countries with high and very high human development.

Results show that religiosity, spirituality, and intergenerational household structures associate with lower environmental impact, while secular-rational and individualistic orientations align with higher impact. Non-denominational spirituality also emerges as significant across contexts, suggesting that spiritual and relational worldviews may be overlooked resources for sustainability policy and education. By contrast, pro-environmental attitudes and indicators of subjective well-being, such as happiness, freedom, and health, do not consistently differentiate between impact groups. Additional factors such as insularity and average national temperature further relate to sustainability outcomes, highlighting the interplay of cultural and structural dimensions.

These findings suggest that current EE frameworks may be too narrowly focused on cognitive and attitudinal factors. To be effective, EE must incorporate spiritual, moral, and communal dimensions, engaging with the plurality of worldviews that guide human–environment relations. More nuanced sustainability indicators, sensitive to cultural and contextual diversity, are needed to better understand and foster comprehensive pathways towards sustainability.

1. Introduction

Understanding what drives human behaviour towards sustainability is key to environmental education (EE), understood as the “approaches, tools, and programs that develop and support environmentally related attitudes, values, awareness, knowledge, and skills that prepare people to take informed action on behalf of the environment” (Ardoin et al., 2020, p. 1). However, these drivers seem to remain elusive to EE policies and programs, which are still far from achieving the desired impact on aggregated levels. Since the UNESCO-led Tbilisi conference of 1977, EE has been considered a global priority. Yet, almost five decades later, UNESCO's (2024) report on learning for sustainability concludes that EE remains insufficiently implemented, and even when delivered, its

effectiveness in catalysing meaningful engagement is limited. The EU Council Recommendation (European Commission, 2022) on learning for environmental sustainability and the EU report (European Commission, 2024) analysing the implementation of the *European sustainability competence framework*, also known as GreenComp, reaffirm this concern, stressing the need to place value-based learning at the core of environmental education.

Meanwhile, anthropogenic global warming denialism remains widespread, often fuelled by cultural disconnection or by the failure of technical language to resonate with people's lived values and beliefs (Marshall, 2014; Hornsey et al., 2018; Vlăsceanu et al., 2024). The *Reuters Institute Digital News Report* (Newman et al., 2020), based on a survey of more than 80,000 respondents across 50 countries, found that,

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on average, 31 % do not consider climate change to be a very serious problem. This tendency is particularly pronounced in various high-impact, high-income countries. For example, in Germany, Australia, the United States, Belgium, Denmark, Sweden, Norway or The Netherlands, only 58 %, 58 %, 56 %, 54 %, 53 %, 50 %, 42 %, and 41 % of respondents, respectively, reported viewing climate change as a very serious or extremely serious concern, even though many of these countries are already experiencing severe consequences of global warming, including heatwaves, droughts, wildfires, marine biodiversity loss, and flooding. This signals a paradox: countries with high environmental impact and abundant access to information, resources, and technology often display lower motivation to change behaviours in favour of climate action, despite being directly affected by its consequences. The challenge deepens when we consider that high risk perception does not necessarily translate into active engagement or behavioural change in favour of effective environmental action (Islam and Winkel, 2017; Daalen et al., 2019; Dietz et al., 2020; Vlăsceanu et al., 2024).

A more recent study by Vlăsceanu et al. (2024) confirmed both the existence of the paradox and the complexity of driving action across climate beliefs –among sceptics and non-sceptics alike. Based on survey data from nearly 60,000 participants across 63 countries, the study found that in wealthy countries such as Norway, the United States, or Saudi Arabia, around 25 % of the population do not believe that climate change either exists or poses a serious threat. In contrast, among the surveyed countries where over 90 % of the population perceive climate change as a serious threat, most are located in the Global South, with the exception of Portugal and Italy. The study also tested a range of expert consensus-based interventions aimed at encouraging belief and action on climate change. These strategies, however, showed limited effectiveness, with a modest impact primarily among those who already accepted the scientific consensus.

This persistent disconnect between climate risk perception, access to information, and behavioural change suggests that current models of environmental education may not be capturing critical cultural, moral, or socio-economic dimensions that relate to how individuals and societies engage with sustainability. If efforts to enhance awareness and knowledge are insufficient to foster collective action, it becomes necessary to explore whether alternative or complementary factors may be associated with more sustainable outcomes. A possible starting point for such inquiry is to examine whether there are countries that currently combine high levels of human development with low environmental impact. If so, do these countries share particular value-based or behavioural characteristics that differentiate them from others with similar developmental status but higher environmental impact? And might such characteristics offer useful insights for rethinking the normative and pedagogical foundations of environmental education and policy?

To explore these questions, this study sets out two main objectives:

- To identify which countries –if any– achieve both high human development and low environmental impact, based on two sustainability datasets: the Global Footprint Network Open Data Platform (Footprint Data Foundation, York University Ecological Footprint Initiative and Global Footprint Network, 2021) and the Sustainable Development Index (Hickel, 2020). Despite identified limitations in the literature (Giampietro and Saltelli, 2014; Brulé, 2022), both databases are widely used, considered valid and reliable, cover a sufficient number of countries, provide long-term trend data, are built on commonly acknowledged indicators, and are constructed using different methodologies, thereby ensuring robustness in country selection.
- To analyse value-based and behavioural patterns in the selected countries using data from the Joint European Values Survey/World Values Survey (2017–2022) (hereinafter EVS/WVS) (Haerpfer et al., 2022), comparing them with countries of similar human development but higher environmental impact.

Although other studies have examined whether any countries can be considered “sustainable” by comparing a range of sustainability indicators (Fanning et al., 2022; Gucciardi and Luzzati, 2024; Radácsi and Sziget, 2024), to ensure better control when integrating data with the World Values Survey, we conducted a new analysis grouping a range of selected countries with high human development into three categories in accordance to environmental impact: low-impact, medium-impact, and high-impact countries. While not identical, our results in country selection are consistent with those reported in the aforementioned studies.

We then conducted a Cramér’s V analysis on 591 categorical variables from the EVS/WVS to identify statistically significant differences in values and beliefs across these three groups. To better understand the context of these differences, we also examined each country’s level of multidimensional poverty (using the UN’s Multidimensional Poverty Index) and its 10-year average temperature, as both factors may be related to variations among countries and groups. This multi-layered approach enables us to identify which values might associate with sustainability, as well as which commonly assumed sustainability-related beliefs do not vary meaningfully across countries despite differences in environmental impact, highlighting deeper cultural and structural patterns that current models of environmental education and indicators of sustainability may be overlooking.

While this study focuses on value patterns, it does not assume that cultural or religious orientations cause differences in environmental impact. National footprints are shaped by a wide range of structural factors, including social, economic, geographic, and political conditions, which are not included in this analysis. By restricting the sample to countries with high or very high human development and comparing groups with different environmental impact levels, the study examines which value configurations co-occur with lower or higher impact under broadly comparable development conditions. This approach does not attribute environmental performance to culture or religion; rather, it highlights cultural factors that remain underexplored yet may be relevant for environmental education policy-making.

2. Methodology

2.1. Selection and grouping of countries

Countries were selected based on two datasets for sustainability: a) the Open Data Platform of the Global Footprint Network (GFN) for sustainable development, and b) the Sustainable Development Index (SDI), here on referred to as GFN and SDI accordingly. The selection criteria for country groups were applied in a stepwise manner, moving from more restrictive thresholds to more inclusive ones until an adequate number of countries was reached in each group with sufficient coverage in the World Values Survey (EVS/WVS). This iterative procedure ensured that the number of countries in each group remained analytically meaningful while also being empirically viable for integration with the EVS/WVS dataset.

2.1.1. Criteria for the selection of low-impact countries

The GFN considers a country is sustainable when its Human Development Index (HDI) as defined by the United Nations is above 0.7, while its ecological footprint, measured as the ecological footprint of consumption per capita (EFConsPC), is below 1.5 global hectares per person. For 2021, which was the latest data available at the time of conducting this analysis, only Egypt, Philippines, Sri Lanka, State of Palestine, and Tunisia complied with these requirements. In order to broaden the sample, we increased the selection to countries with ecological footprint of consumption per capita (EFConsPC) below 2.0 global hectares per person, for a total list of 16 countries as seen in Table 1.

The SDI, developed within the Institute of Environmental Science and Technology of the Autonomous University of Barcelona (ICTA-

Table 1

Low-impact countries with high human development according to the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and the Global Footprint Network (GFN).

Low-impact countries in accordance to the GFN			Low-impact countries in accordance to the SDI	
Country	EFConsPC ≤2	HDI ≥0.7	Country	SDI ≥0.8
State of Palestine	0.67	0.71	Costa Rica	0.833
Sri Lanka	1.05	0.78	Uruguay	0.832
Philippines	1.2	0.7	Sri Lanka	0.832
Jordan	1.35	0.72	Dominican Republic	0.815
Tunisia	1.38	0.73	Barbados	0.813
Egypt	1.45	0.73	Ecuador	0.809
Bahamas	1.55	0.81	Albania	0.808
Indonesia	1.59	0.7	Peru	0.803
Republic of Moldova	1.68	0.77	Colombia	0.801
Ecuador	1.71	0.74	Cuba	0.797
Saint Lucia	1.72	0.71	Georgia	0.796
Jamaica	1.76	0.71	Thailand	0.795
Grenada	1.77	0.8		
Dominican Republic	1.85	0.77		
Saint Vincent and Grenadines	1.88	0.75		
Cuba	1.92	0.76		

Caption for Table 1. Countries with low-impact and high human development according to the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and the Global Footprint Network (GFN). Table 1 presents the classification of low-impact countries based on two distinct datasets: the Global Footprint Network (GFN), which considers countries with a Human Development Index (HDI) of at least 0.7 and an Ecological Footprint of Consumption per Capita (EFConsPC) of at least 2 global hectares, and the Sustainable Development Index (SDI), which includes countries with an SDI of at least 0.8. On the left, countries meeting the GFN criteria; on the right, countries meeting the SDI criteria. Countries in bold appear in both datasets with the selection criteria.

UAB), updates the United Nations Human Development Index (HDI) by factoring in overshoot of CO2 emissions and material footprint of countries. The index is calculated as a 3-decimal number between 0 and 1, where the higher the SDI, the more sustainable a country is. Costa Rica was the highest ranking country for 2022, which is the year corresponding to the latest available data at the time of conducting this analysis, with a SDI of 0.833. We selected all countries rounding up to a SDI of 0.8 or higher (>0.755) yielding a list of 12 countries as seen in Table 1.

The final list of GFN-based and SDI-based selected countries for low environmental impact with high human development is indicated in Table 1, where Cuba, Dominican Republic, Ecuador and Sri Lanka were the only four countries coinciding in both data sets under the given criteria:

When expanding the selection criteria to HDI >0.7 and EF < 3 for the GFN database and to SDI ≥0.75, all selected countries matched across both databases, except for the Bahamas (with an SDI of 0.476), and Grenada, Moldova, Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, and the State of Palestine, which are not included in the SDI database. This suggests that, despite methodological differences between the datasets, these differences are not overly significant.

2.1.2. Criteria for the selection of medium-impact countries

To identify medium-impact countries, we applied a two-step selection process to the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and the Global Footprint Network (GFN) indicators. In the first iteration, countries were selected based on the following:

- Using SDI data: an SDI ranking of up to place 82 (out of 163 countries listed), with a life expectancy of at least 80 years (rounded from 79.5), excluding countries that were already listed in the low-impact group;

- Using GFN data: an HDI above 0.9 (rounded from 0.85) and an ecological footprint of consumption per capita between 2 and 4 global hectares per person (rounded down from 4.4).

Applying these criteria targeted countries that perform moderately well in sustainable development, that is, moderate environmental impact with very high human development standards.

To assure that the country selection was coherent with both sets of data – SDI and GFN – we applied a second iteration, cross-checking each country from the first iteration in the other database, as shown in

Table 2

Selection process for the medium-impact country group.

	Medium-impact countries in accordance to the SDI	Medium-impact countries in accordance to the GFN
First iteration	Portugal	Chile
<i>For SDI: countries ranking up to 82 out 163 in SDI, with life expectancy above 80 (rounded up from 79.5), excluding countries included in the low-impact group.</i>	Greece	Croatia
	Malta	France
	Spain	Greece
	Chile	Cyprus
	Italy	Malta
	France	Ireland
<i>For GFN: countries with HDI above 0.9 (rounded up from 0.85), and above 2 and up to 4 global hectares per person (rounded down from 4.4)</i>		Israel
		Italy
		Japan
		Portugal
		Spain
		Switzerland
		United Kingdom
Countries not meeting the selection criteria in second iteration	(all countries met threshold in first and second iteration)	Cyprus
<i>For SDI selected countries in first iteration: countries with HDI above 0.9 (rounded up from 0.85), and above 2 and up to 4 global hectares per person (rounded down from 4.4) in accordance to GFN</i>		Ireland
<i>For GFN selected countries in first iteration: countries ranking up to 82 out 163 in SDI, with life expectancy above 79*, excluding countries included in the low-impact group.</i>		Israel
<i>*Threshold lowered 0.5 points to avoid excluding Croatia due to threshold sensitivity</i>		Japan
		Switzerland
		United Kingdom
Final list	Portugal	
	Greece	
	Malta	
	Spain	
	Chile	
	Italy	
	France	
	Croatia	

Caption for Table 2. Selection process for medium-impact countries according to the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and the Global Footprint Network (GFN). Table 2 outlines the classification procedure in two iterations: for the SDI, countries ranked up to 82 out of 163 with a life expectancy above 80 (rounded from 79.5) and not already included in the low-impact group; for the GFN, countries with a Human Development Index (HDI) above 0.9 (rounded from 0.85) and an Ecological Footprint of Consumption per Capita (EFConsPC) between 2 and 4 global hectares per person (rounded down from 4.4). In the second iteration, SDI countries were checked against GFN criteria and viceversa. All SDI countries met both iterations, while Cyprus, Ireland, Israel, Japan, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom were excluded from the GFN group in the second iteration for being ranked above 90 in the SDI list. Croatia ranked 40th in the SDI, with an HDI of 0.86 and a life expectancy of 79.2. To avoid excluding Croatia due to threshold sensitivity, the life expectancy threshold was adjusted to 79.0. The final list of medium-impact countries includes Portugal, Greece, Malta, Spain, Chile, Italy, France, and Croatia.

Table 3
Selection process for the high-impact country group.

	High-impact countries in accordance to the SDI	High-impact countries in accordance to the GFN
First iteration		
<i>For SDI: countries with rank 140 and over and life expectancy > 80 (rounded up from 79.5)</i>	Austria Israel New Zealand Korea	Australia Austria Bahrain Belgium
<i>For GFN: countries with HDI > 0,9 (rounded up from 0.85) and EFConsPC > 6 (rounded up from 5.5)</i>	Ireland Netherlands Finland Switzerland Belgium Iceland Australia Norway Canada Singapore Luxembourg Kuwait Hong Kong SAR, China Qatar	Canada Denmark Estonia Iceland Latvia Lithuania Luxembourg Netherlands Qatar Republic of Korea Saudi Arabia Singapore United Arab Emirates United States of America
Countries not meeting the selection criteria in second iteration	Israel New Zealand Ireland Finland Switzerland Hong Kong SAR, China	Bahrain Estonia Latvia Lithuania
<i>For SDI: countries with HDI > 0.83 and EFConsPC > 5.4</i>		
<i>For GFN: countries with rank in SDI > 135 and life expectancy > 78</i>		
Final list	Australia Austria Belgium Canada Denmark Iceland Kuwait Luxembourg Netherlands Norway Qatar Republic of Korea (South Korea) Saudi Arabia Singapore United Arab Emirates United States of America	

Caption for Table 3. Selection process for high-impact countries according to the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and the Global Footprint Network (GFN). Table 3 presents the classification procedure in two iterations: for the SDI, countries ranked 140 or higher with a life expectancy above 80 (rounded from 79.5), and for the GFN, countries with a Human Development Index (HDI) above 0.9 (rounded from 0.85) and an Ecological Footprint of Consumption per Capita (EFConsPC) above 6 (rounded from 5.5). In the second iteration, SDI criteria were broadened to HDI above 0.83 and EFConsPC above 5.4, while GFN criteria included countries with an SDI rank above 135 and life expectancy above 78. The final list of high-impact countries includes Australia, Austria, Bahrain, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Iceland, Kuwait, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Qatar, Republic of Korea (South Korea), Saudi Arabia, Singapore, United Arab Emirates, and the United States of America.

Table 2. This selection process ensured a robust classification aligning with established sustainability benchmarks of both datasets.

2.1.3. Criteria for the selection of high-impact countries

In an equivalent process to the selection of medium-impact countries, to select high-impact countries the criteria was as follows:

- Based on the SDI data: an SDI ranking above 140 (out of 163 countries listed), with a life expectancy of at least 80 years (rounded from 79.5);

- Based on the GFN data: an HDI above 0.9 (rounded from 0.85) and an ecological footprint of consumption per capita above 6 global hectares per person (rounded up from 5.5).

Applying these criteria targeted countries with high human development standards but a significant environmental impact, ensuring the selection focused on nations exerting substantial environmental pressure.

To assure that the country selection was coherent with both sets of data –SDI and GFN– we applied a second iteration to the selection that resulted from the first iteration. Countries listed from the GFN list were required to have an SDI rank above 135 and a life expectancy above 78, while countries listed from the SDI needed to have a minimum HDI of 0.83 and a minimum EFConsPC of 5.4.

The final list for the high-impact country group was as follows:

2.1.4. Threshold sensitivity and robustness of country classification

The classification of countries into low-, medium-, and high-impact groups draws on internationally recognised sustainability thresholds used by the Global Footprint Network (GFN) and the Sustainable Development Index (SDI), which operationalise sustainability as achieving high human development within planetary boundaries. These criteria are widely applied in cross-national sustainability research, and recent analyses using alternative boundary metrics (e.g., Fanning et al., 2022; Radácsi and Szigeti, 2024) identify comparable sets of low-impact countries, supporting the external validity of this approach. To minimise dependence on a single cut-off, a stepwise selection procedure was employed, beginning with the most stringent thresholds and progressively widening them to ensure sufficient case coverage while retaining conceptual coherence. This iterative procedure served as a built-in sensitivity check, with country groupings remaining stable across adjacent threshold bands and across both datasets. While quartile-based grouping or data-driven clustering could also be applied to explore alternative boundaries, the consistency across threshold bands and data sources in this study suggests that the observed value patterns reflect substantive cross-national differences rather than artefacts of threshold selection. Table 4 summarizes all applied thresholds and their rationales.

2.1.5. Preparing for integration of SDI and GFN with EVS/WVS

In a last step, countries were selected based on whether they appeared in the Joint European Value Survey/World Value Survey (2017–2022) in order to undertake the statistical analysis. The final list of countries appearing in the EVS/WVS (2017–2022) was as follows:

2.2. Integration with the World Values Survey

The Joint European Value Survey/World Value Survey (2017–2022) provides representative samples for total populations of the countries under study. Table 6 indicates the sample sizes.

Using SPSS, the country groups were coded as low-impact, medium-impact and high-impact. A total of 591 variables were analysed using a Cramér’s V statistical analysis for categorical variables in contingency tables. The analysis was repeated three times to assure consistency:

- The first analysis compared the low-impact country group as listed in the SDI dataset and that appeared in the EVS/WVS (Ecuador, Uruguay, Peru, Colombia, and Thailand) with the groups of medium and high-impact countries. A total of 44,492 individual interviews were processed divided in the three groups.
- The second analysis compared the low-impact country group as listed in the GFN dataset and that appeared in the EVS/WVS (Ecuador, Egypt, Indonesia, Jordan, Philippines, and Tunisia) with the groups of medium and high-impact countries. A total of 43,454 individual interviews were processed divided in the three groups.

Table 4
Summary of applied thresholds for country group selection.

Thresholds for low-impact country group selection				
Indicator	Data Source	Threshold Used	Applied To/Group	Rationale
Human Development Index (HDI)	UNDP via Global Footprint Network	HDI ≥ 0.7	GFN country list	Baseline for all selected countries. Ensures countries are not low-impact due to acute poverty; establishes human development conditions in accordance to international standards for high and very high development.
Ecological Footprint (EFConsPC)	Global Footprint Network	EF < 1.5 gha	GFN country list	Conceptual sustainability benchmark for low-impact group selection based on the GFN dataset, based on the standard “one-planet” sustainability threshold used by the Global Footprint Network (HDI ≥ 0.7 and EFConsPC < 1.5). At this level, for 2021 data, only a very small number of countries qualify (State of Palestine, Sri Lanka, Philippines, Jordan, Tunisia, Egypt), and just four of them (Egypt, Jordan, Philippines, Tunisia) are covered in the EVS/WVS 2017–2022 dataset. This yielded an analytically very small and regionally narrow low-impact group.
Ecological Footprint (EFConsPC)	Global Footprint Network	EF < 2 gha	GFN country list	GFN sustainability threshold expanded to EFConsPC ≤ 2.0 gha to preserve conceptual proximity to the one-planet boundary while obtaining a more diverse and statistically meaningful low-impact group. This second iteration brought the total to 16 GFN low-impact countries (Table 1), and increased the number of low-impact countries with EVS/WVS data to 6 (Egypt, Indonesia, Jordan, Philippines, Tunisia, Ecuador). These countries remain clearly below the ecological footprint levels of the medium- and high-impact groups, so the conceptual distinction between impact groups is retained.
Sustainable Development Index (SDI)	Sustainable Development Index	SDI ≥ 0.8	SDI country list	The SDI provides no conceptual boundary for defining sustainability performance. To operationalise a threshold, the distribution of SDI scores was reviewed in 0.1-point increments. No country scores above 0.9, and only twelve countries fall in the 0.8–1.0 range, forming the group for “top performers” in sustainable development (Hickel, 2020). As the SDI is reported to three decimals, the cut-off was rounded to ≥ 0.800 (i.e., including countries scoring 0.795 and above) to avoid excluding borderline cases.
SDI and GFN low-impact group robustness check	SDI and Global Footprint Network	SDI ≥ 0.75 and EF < 3.0 gha	Selected GFN and SDI low-impact country list	At the expanded thresholds (SDI ≥ 0.75 and EF < 3 gha), all countries identified as low-impact in one dataset are also captured within the corresponding broadened group of the other dataset, with two substantive and several technical exceptions. On the SDI side, the only GFN low-impact country not included is the Bahamas, which has a low SDI rank (123). On the GFN side, the only SDI ≥ 0.8 country excluded is Barbados, whose ecological footprint slightly exceeds the expanded EF < 3 gha threshold (3.17 gha). Additional GFN low-impact cases (Grenada, Republic of Moldova, Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, and the State of Palestine) are absent from the SDI dataset and therefore cannot be evaluated for overlap. Aside from these data-availability limitations and the two threshold-sensitive outliers, the core set of countries consistently appears across both sustainability frameworks, indicating strong robustness of the identified group under reasonable threshold variation.
Thresholds for mid-impact country group selection				
Indicator	Data Source	Threshold Used	Applied To/Group	Rationale
SDI and Life expectancy	Sustainable Development Index	SDI rank ≤ 82 (top 50 % of countries of 163) and life expectancy ≥ 80 years (rounded from 79.5), excluding low-impact countries	SDI country list	This threshold selects the upper half of SDI performers who do not meet the stricter SDI ≥ 0.8 low-impact criterion. The SDI is calculated using life expectancy, expected years of schooling, mean years of schooling, income (GNI per capita, constant 2017 PPP), CO ₂ emissions, and material footprint. To ensure that the mid-impact group reflects top HDI performers within the highest-ranked 50 % of SDI countries, we applied a second filter based on life expectancy, an indicator already used in the SDI formulation. This step helps ensure that countries included in the mid-impact group maintain consistently very high human development levels, given their environmental impact.
Human Development Index (HDI) and Ecological Footprint (EFConsPC)	Global Footprint Network	HDI ≥ 0.8 and $2 \leq$ EFConsPC < 4 gha (rounded from 4.4)	GFN country list	Ensures that GFN-selected countries for mid-impact meet the internationally recognised “very high human development” category (HDI ≥ 0.8), while maintaining a mid-impact range for ecological footprint, to produce a consistent approach to “top performers” in mid-range impact within the GFN dataset.
Second-iteration GFN/SDI cross-check	Global Footprint Network	HDI ≥ 0.8 and $2 \leq$ EFConsPC < 4 gha (rounded from 4.4)	SDI selected mid-impact group in first iteration	Ensures that mid-impact SDI-selected countries are also in the mid-impact range in the GFN dataset.
Second-iteration GFN/SDI cross-check	Sustainable Development Index	SDI rank ≤ 82 (top 50 % of countries of 163) and life expectancy ≥ 80 years (rounded from 79), excluding low-impact countries	GFN selected mid-impact group in first iteration	Ensures that mid-impact GFN-selected countries are also in the mid-impact range in the SDI dataset. There was a clear break in SDI ranking with Portugal, Greece, Malta, Spain, Chile, Italy, France, and Croatia ranking less than 78 in SDI, while a second group composed of Cyprus, Ireland, Israel, Japan, Switzerland and United Kingdom were all ranked above 133. Rank threshold was left at 82

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Thresholds for mid-impact country group selection				
Indicator	Data Source	Threshold Used	Applied To/Group	Rationale
				and this second group was discarded. Out of the remaining group, Croatia ranked 40 in SDI, with HDI of 0.86 and with life expectancy of 79.2. So in order to include Croatia to avoid exclusion due to threshold sensitivity the life expectancy threshold was lowered to 79.0.
Thresholds for high-impact country group selection				
Indicator	Data Source	Threshold Used	Applied To/Group	Rationale
SDI ranking and life expectancy	Sustainable Development Index	SDI rank ≥ 140 and life expectancy ≥ 80 years (rounded from 79.5)	SDI country list	Selects countries with very high human development that also exhibit the highest levels of environmental impact according to the SDI ranking. Setting the threshold at rank 140 ensures a sufficiently large group with EVS/WVS coverage, while maintaining a clear separation from the mid-impact range in terms of ecological pressure.
Human Development Index (HDI) and Ecological Footprint (EFConsPC)	Global Footprint Network	HDI ≥ 0.9 (rounded from 0.85) and EFConsPC > 6 gha (rounded from 5.5)	GFN country list	Selects countries with very high human development that also exhibit the highest levels of environmental impact according to the GFN country list. Setting the threshold at 6 gha ensures a sufficiently large group with EVS/WVS coverage, while maintaining a clear separation from the mid-impact range in terms of ecological pressure.
Second-iteration SDI cross-check	Sustainable Development Index	Minimum HDI ≥ 0.83 and EFConsPC ≥ 5.4	SDI selected high-impact group in first iteration	To ensure consistency between SDI- and GFN-selected high-impact countries, the initial strict thresholds (SDI rank ≥ 140 ; life expectancy ≥ 80 ; HDI ≥ 0.90 ; EFConsPC > 6.0) were widened in a second iteration by small numerical increments to account for rounding differences and dataset-construction disparities. For SDI-selected countries, the GFN cross-check thresholds were lowered from HDI ≥ 0.90 to ≥ 0.83 and from EFConsPC > 6.0 to ≥ 5.4 . For GFN-selected countries, the SDI cross-check was reduced from rank ≥ 140 to ≥ 135 and life expectancy from ≥ 80 to ≥ 78 . Expansion stopped once both datasets produced a stable, overlapping set of high-impact countries, ensuring that the final group reflected consistent high human development and high environmental impact, with sufficient diversity in population size, geography, and socio-cultural context among countries covered by the EVS/WVS.
Second-iteration GFN cross-check	Global Footprint Network	SDI rank ≥ 135 and life expectancy ≥ 78	GFN selected high-impact group in first iteration	

Caption for Table 4. Summary of applied thresholds for country group selection. Summary of threshold criteria applied to define low-, mid-, and high-impact country groups across SDI and GFN datasets.

- The third analysis compared the low-impact country group from both datasets that appeared in the EVS/WVS with the groups of medium and high-impact countries. A total of 52,503 individual interviews were processed divided in the three groups.

The variables selected as significant had to yield a strong association among the three analysed groups consistently across the three statistical analysis undertaken, with a Cramér’s V equal to or above 0.3 in all three steps. The threshold of Cramér’s V ≥ 0.3 was selected to isolate strong and substantively meaningful associations, following effect-size conventions for chi-square-based measures in the behavioural sciences (Cohen, 1988) and as discussed in Ben-Shachar et al. (2023). With a very large sample (N = 52,503) and 591 categorical variables, smaller V values, although statistically significant, would risk reflecting trivial differences inflated by sample size. A stricter cut-off was therefore needed to ensure that retained associations are genuinely meaningful. In addition, because the analysis was run three times using different country groupings (SDI, GFN, and combined), only variables reaching V ≥ 0.3 in all three analyses were included, ensuring robustness across datasets. This conservative approach keeps the focus on value patterns that consistently differentiate low-, medium-, and high-impact countries.

3. Results

3.1. Association between the sustainability databases and the VWS culture map

The first result of integrating the sustainability and value databases

came unexpectedly after country selection for group composition, and before even beginning the statistical analysis. The low-impact, medium-impact and high-impact country groups selected turned out to closely correspond with the Inglehart-Welzel World Cultural Map (Fig. 1), which was developed based on value and behavioural pattern identification of World Values Survey results across waves.

The map distinguishes two major dimensions of cross cultural variation in the world: a) traditional values versus secular-rational values; and b) survival values versus self-expression values, defined as follows (Inglehart and Welzel, 2005):

- “Traditional values: Emphasize the importance of religion, parent-child ties, deference to authority and traditional family values. People who embrace these values also reject divorce, abortion, euthanasia and suicide. These societies have high levels of national pride and a nationalistic outlook.
- Secular-rational values: Have the opposite preferences to the traditional values. These societies place less emphasis on religion, traditional family values and authority. Divorce, abortion, euthanasia and suicide are seen as relatively acceptable. (Suicide is not necessarily more common.)
- Survival values: Place emphasis on economic and physical security. It is linked with a relatively ethnocentric outlook and low levels of trust and tolerance.
- Self-expression values: Give high priority to environmental protection, growing tolerance of foreigners, gays and lesbians and gender equality, and rising demands for participation in decision-making in economic and political life.”

When looking closely at how the different country groups selected

Table 5
Selection process based on inclusion of the country in the Joint European Value Survey/World Value Survey (2017–2022).

Group composition for statistical analysis	Sub-selection of countries listed in the EVS/WVS (2017–2022)	Total population of the group
Low-impact	Ecuador (SDI + GFN) (GFN) Egypt Uruguay Indonesia Peru Jordan Colombia Philippines Albania Tunisia Georgia Thailand	704,976,046
Mid-impact	Portugal Greece Spain Chile Italy France Croatia	216,145,188
High-impact	Australia Austria Canada Denmark Iceland Netherlands Norway Republic of Korea (South Korea) Singapore United States of America	496,923,351

Caption for Table 5. Selection of countries based on inclusion in the Joint European Values Survey/World Values Survey (EVS/WVS, 2017–2022). Table 5 presents the final composition of low-, medium-, and high-impact country groups retained for the statistical analysis. Only countries appearing in the EVS/WVS dataset were included. The resulting groups comprise: low-impact countries (Ecuador, Egypt, Indonesia, Jordan, Philippines, Tunisia, Uruguay, Peru, Colombia, Albania, Georgia, Thailand), mid-impact countries (Portugal, Greece, Spain, Chile, Italy, France, Croatia), and high-impact countries (Australia, Austria, Canada, Denmark, Iceland, Netherlands, Norway, Republic of Korea, Singapore, United States of America). The total population represented in each group is also shown.

from the SDI and GFN are framed within the map, we have the following result:

The map shows a strong association between traditional/secular and survival/self-expression values with environmental impact amongst countries with high and very high HDI. More traditional and survivalist countries tend to exhibit lower environmental impact, while countries that are more oriented towards secularity and self-expression have higher environmental impact. Outliers in this association are Singapore, South Korea, Uruguay and Thailand. It is important to note that association does not mean causality, and that other factors could be explaining this association. In the discussion section, we will address this further, as well as the limitations of using the Inglehart-Welzel map as an analytical source to determine sustainability standards.

To further illustrate the cultural composition underlying these value clusters, Table 7 presents the aggregated religious affiliation profiles of each sustainability impact group, offering a complementary perspective on the cultural differences reflected in the Inglehart–Welzel map.

The denominational distributions in Table 7 further clarify the cultural configurations reflected in the Inglehart–Welzel map. Low-impact countries display a predominantly religious profile, with substantial shares of Muslim, Buddhist, Orthodox, and Catholic affiliation. The GFN-based group in particular is characterised by a strong Muslim presence, reflecting North African and Southeast Asian contexts. Medium-impact countries are overwhelmingly Catholic, consistent with Southern European societies occupying intermediate positions on the cultural map. High-impact countries, by contrast, show the highest share

Table 6
Sample sizes.

Country	Low-impact	Mid-impact	High-impact	Total
Albania (SDI)	1435	0	0	1435
Colombia (SDI)	1520	0	0	1520
Ecuador (SDI + GFN)	1200	0	0	1200
Peru (SDI)	1400	0	0	1400
Uruguay (SDI)	1000	0	0	1000
Thailand (SDI)	1500	0	0	1500
Philippines (GFN)	1200	0	0	1200
Indonesia (GFN)	3200	0	0	3200
Georgia (GFN)	2194	0	0	2194
Tunisia (GFN)	1208	0	0	1208
Egypt (GFN)	1200	0	0	1200
Jordan (GFN)	1203	0	0	1203
Chile	0	1000	0	1000
France	0	1870	0	1870
Spain	0	1209	0	1209
Portugal	0	1215	0	1215
Italy	0	2277	0	2277
Croatia	0	1487	0	1487
Greece	0	1200	0	1200
Norway	0	0	1122	1122
Denmark	0	0	3362	3362
Iceland	0	0	1624	1624
South Korea	0	0	1245	1245
Australia	0	0	1813	1813
Austria	0	0	1644	1644
Canada	0	0	4018	4018
Netherlands	0	0	4549	4549
Singapore	0	0	2012	2012
United States of America	0	0	2596	2596
TOTAL	18260	10258	23985	52503

Caption for Table 6. Sample sizes by country and sustainability impact group. Number of respondents included in each country-level sample according to classification into low-, mid-, and high-impact groups based on sustainability thresholds from the Global Footprint Network (GFN) and the Sustainable Development Index (SDI). Total sample size = 52,503.

of respondents with no religious denomination and a notable concentration of Protestant affiliation, aligning with secular-rational and self-expression value patterns. These differences illustrate meaningful cultural variation across sustainability groups.

At the same time, these patterns underscore the need to complement aggregate-level interpretation with country-specific analysis. First, the absence of religious denomination should not be equated with the absence of spirituality; as shown later, a significant share of respondents who do not identify with a religious tradition nonetheless express belief in God or spiritual orientations. Second, the data do not suggest that sustainability aligns more consistently with one religious tradition than another; lower environmental impact appears across diverse cultural and denominational settings. Third, this indicates that sustainability may be less about whether individuals identify as religious and more about how moral commitments, community ties, and normative expectations are practiced and institutionalised in each context. In other words, religiosity may offer resources that support sustainable orientations in some settings, but it is neither a prerequisite for lower impact nor a guarantee of it. Finally, the patterns observed align more strongly with the traditional versus secular-rational and survival versus self-expression cultural axes than with specific denominations, suggesting that underlying value configurations around authority, community, responsibility, and consumption norms may be more consequential for sustainability than formal religious belonging.

3.2. Insularity

The analysis conducted prior to EVS/WVS selection indicates that the GFN classification yields insularity as a relevant factor in sustainability, where islands are significantly overrepresented in the low-impact group, moderately overrepresented in the medium-impact group, and

Fig. 1. The Inglehart-Welzel World Value Survey 7, 2023
Caption for Fig. 1. Inglehart–Welzel cultural map of the world based on data from the World Values Survey and the European Values Study (1981–2022). The map positions countries along two main cultural dimensions: Traditional vs. Secular-Rational Values (vertical axis) and Survival vs. Self-Expression Values (horizontal axis). Countries are clustered into broader cultural regions, including African-Islamic, Latin America, Confucian, Orthodox Europe, Catholic Europe, Protestant Europe, English-Speaking, and West & South Asia. (World Value Survey 7, 2023).

Fig. 2. The Inglehart-Welzel World Cultural Map for low, medium and high environmental impact countries with high and very high human development index
Caption for Fig. 2. The Inglehart–Welzel World Cultural Map with the integration of environmental impact groups derived from the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and the Global Footprint Network (GFN). Countries with high and very high Human Development Index (HDI) were classified into low-, medium-, and high-impact groups based on the combined SDI and GFN selection process and then mapped onto the cultural dimensions of the World Values Survey (WVS): Traditional vs. Secular-Rational Values (vertical axis) and Survival vs. Self-Expression Values (horizontal axis). Group membership is indicated as follows: low-impact countries (green), medium-impact countries (blue), and high-impact countries (red). Made by the author based on data from the SDI, the GFN, and the World Values Survey & European Values Study (2005–2023) Inglehart–Welzel World Cultural Map.

underrepresented in the high-impact group in comparison to the island to mainland ratio for the world, as shown in Table 8. However, insularity as a potential underlying factor in sustainability does not hold under the SDI classification. This highlights methodological differences amongst datasets that require further study.

3.3. Statistically significant variables amongst groups

Once the statistical analysis was undertaken using SPSS, we identified the significant variables, which are presented in Table 9.

Other significant variables were “Occupational group – respondent” and “Occupational group – respondent’s spouse,” which were discarded as they were only included in the World Values Survey and not the European Values Survey, meaning the results were based on a minimal number of responses.

Additionally, in order to focus the analysis, the variables related to the respondent’s perception of “Justifiable: Homosexuality” and “Justifiable: Abortion” were excluded, despite being of statistically significant. These variables strongly correlate with the variable “Pertaining to a religious denomination”, making them more indicative of

Table 7
Religious composition across country groups.

Religious denomination	SDI Country Group (%)	GFN Country Group (%)	SDI + GFN Country Group (%)	Mid-impact Country Group (%)	High-impact Country Group (%)
Do not belong to a denomination	20.9 %	5.0 %	11.9 %	28.3 %	40.5 %
Roman Catholic	25.1 %	18.2 %	19.9 %	53.3 %	17.4 %
Protestant	4.5 %	5.5 %	4.6 %	1.4 %	28.5 %
Orthodox (Russian/Greek/etc.)	19.1 %	0.0 %	10.7 %	11.1 %	0.7 %
Jew	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.2 %	0.6 %
Muslim	13.5 %	68.3 %	42.0 %	1.6 %	2.6 %
Hindu	0.0 %	1.1 %	0.6 %	0.1 %	1.0 %
Buddhist	13.5 %	0.1 %	7.6 %	0.2 %	3.5 %
Other Christian (Evangelical/Pentecostal/Free church/etc.)	2.4 %	1.3 %	1.9 %	0.4 %	2.6 %
Other	1.0 %	0.6 %	0.8 %	3.5 %	2.6 %

Caption for Table 7. Religious composition across country groups. Table 6 summarizes the religious composition of each country group, reporting aggregated denominational distributions for low-, medium-, and high-impact countries. For the low-impact category, results are shown separately for countries selected through the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and those identified through the Global Footprint Network (GFN), illustrating cultural variation across groups. Medium- and high-impact groups are presented as pooled distributions. These data help contextualise value patterns observed in the analysis. Results are presented as percentages of respondents by group. Source: SPSS processing of harmonized WVS/EVS Wave 7 microdata integrated with country group selection based on SDI and GFN sustainability databases.

Table 8
Island to mainland ratio of country groups according to GFN and SDI datasets.

Country groups selected on first iteration	Insularity ratio based on the Global Footprint Network country selection	Insularity ratio based on the Sustainable Development Index country selection
Low-impact	10:6 = 1.67	4:8 = 0.5
Medium-impact	5:9 = 0.56	1:6 = 0.17
High-impact	4:14 = 0.29	6:12 = 0.5
World	47:148 = 0.32	

Caption for Table 8. Island-to-mainland ratio of low-, medium-, and high-impact country groups according to the Global Footprint Network (GFN) and Sustainable Development Index (SDI) datasets. Ratios are calculated as the number of island countries to mainland countries within each group, based on the first iteration of country selection. The world average ratio (47:148 = 0.32) is provided for reference.

conservative moral values, than providing insight into the values underlying sustainability, which is the primary objective of this analysis. Nevertheless, further research into the nuanced relationship between the acceptance of homosexuality and abortion and sustainability practices could shed light on whether specific causal links exist that are not mediated by religion.

The variable “How important is God in your life” also correlates with the variable “Pertaining to a religious denomination.” However, the gap between the “% of respondents that do not belong to a denomination” and the “% of respondents that indicate God to be not at all important in their lives” is relevant. This gap highlights the presence of non-denominational spirituality or some form of deism, which may be an important area of study for understanding the values shaping sustainability.

Non-denominational spirituality can be inferred by comparing the percentage of respondents who report not belonging to a religious

Table 9
Statistically significant variables showcasing differences amongst low, mid and high-impact country groups based on World Values Survey integration with SDI and GFN sustainability databases.

Statistically significant variables (Cramér’s $V \geq 0.3$ for all three analysis, where: Analysis 1: only SDI countries in the low-impact group; Analysis 2: GFN + SDI countries in the low-impact group; Analysis 3: only GFN countries in the low-impact group)		Results for the three groups		
		Low-impact (SDI/GFN + SDI/GFN)	Medium-impact	High-impact
It is a child’s duty to take care of an ill parent	% of respondents that strongly agree or agree	82.6 %/86.6 %/90.9 %	71.3 %	35.2 %
How often in a country’s elections: Voters are bribed	% of respondents that indicate very often or fairly often	68.9 %/65.8 %/63.6 %	44.1 %	36.4 %
Religious denomination	% of respondents that do not belong to a denomination	20.9 %/11.9 %/5.0 %	28.3 %	40.5 %
How important is God in your life	% of respondents that indicate not at all important	7.5 %/5.5 %/2.7 %	14.7 %	26.6 %
	% of respondents that indicate very important	63.9 %/73.3 %/84.1 %	24.3 %	15.6 %
Most people can be trusted	% of respondents indicating most people can be trusted	10.6 %/9.7 %/8.2 %	23.2 %	55 %
	% of respondents indicating can’t be too careful	89.4 %/90.3 %/91.8 %	76.8 %	45 %
Number of people in a household	% of respondents living in households of 1 person	5.9 %/5.0 %/4.1 %	22.1 %	19.8 %
	% of respondents living in households of 1 or 2 people	19.9 %/17.7 %/16.3 %	54.9 %	56.1 %
	% of respondents living in households of 5 or more people	44.2 %/43.3 %/42.1 %	8.3 %	9.8 %
	% of respondents living in households of 6 or more people	28.8 %/26.6 %/24.0 %	2.5 %	3.3 %

Caption for Table 9. Statistically significant variables differentiating low-, medium-, and high-impact country groups based on the SPSS analysis of World Values Survey (EVS/WVS) harmonized dataset after country group integration based on the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) and Global Footprint Network (GFN) sustainability databases. Variables included met the threshold of Cramér’s $V \geq 0.3$ across three analyses: (1) only SDI countries in the low-impact group, (2) GFN + SDI countries in the low-impact group, and (3) only GFN countries in the low-impact group. Results are presented as percentages of respondents by group. Variable codebook accessible at: <https://www.worldvaluessurvey.org/WVSEVSjoint2017.jsp>.

denomination with the percentage who state that God is not important in their lives. The difference between these two indicators points to a group who, despite not identifying with any denomination, still consider God to hold at least some importance. In the low-impact group, 20.9 % (SDI countries), 11.9 % (GFN + SDI countries), and 5.0 % (GFN countries) indicate no denominational affiliation, while only 7.5 %, 5.5 %, and 2.7 % respectively report that God is not important at all. In medium-impact countries, 28.3 % report no denominational affiliation, but only 14.7 % consider God not important; in high-impact countries, 40.5 % are unaffiliated while 26.6 % consider God not important. These patterns indicate that around 14 % of respondents in the low-impact

(SDI group), medium-impact, and high-impact groups hold some form of non-denominational belief in God, suggesting that this orientation is significant across contexts.

Although this analysis focuses on cultural orientations, socioeconomic structures also shape sustainability outcomes. To reduce baseline structural heterogeneity, the study is limited to countries with high and very high HDI, meaning that basic education, income, and life-expectancy conditions are already broadly comparable across groups. Within this relatively homogeneous socioeconomic sample, most socioeconomic indicators did not show statistically significant differences between low-, medium-, and high-impact groups, suggesting that the cultural patterns identified are not simply reflections of underlying socioeconomic disparities. The main exception concerns governance-related perceptions: respondents in low-impact groups were more likely to report experiences of electoral bribery and to express stronger norms of filial obligation (Table 8), reflecting sociopolitical contexts where communal responsibilities are emphasised alongside lower institutional trust. These contrasts appear consistent with the traditional-survival side of the cultural map rather than with formal socioeconomic stratification. Nonetheless, governance models, inequality levels, and state capacity may still interact with cultural orientations, and future work could explicitly incorporate such variables –through multivariate designs or mixed-methods approaches– to better disentangle how cultural and structural dynamics jointly shape sustainability pathways.

3.4. Sustainability-related variables that did not yield statistically-significant differences amongst groups

A selection of diverse variables that could be indicative of values underlying sustainability were analysed, to determine if there was an association among low, medium and high environmental impact. For instance, feeling of happiness, feeling of freedom of choice and control and feeling healthy should be important values in sustainable societies, and these subjective indicators are relevant factors to further understand differences in the quality of life in societies with high and very high development index, and whether or not there is a trade-off in subjective wellbeing (health, happiness and freedom) and environmental impact.

Other variables that might be indicative of sustainable values, and which we chose to analyse more closely, were those related to environmental beliefs (“Member: Belong to conservation, the environment, ecology, animal rights group”; “Confidence: The Environmental Protection Movement”; “Protecting environment vs. Economic growth”), those related to a sense of global interconnectedness beyond national borders (“Confidence: The United Nations”; “How close you feel: World”), and self-positioning in the political scale.

There are interesting associations amongst these values themselves, which have been thoroughly studied in literature based on WVS data, such as the relationship between left-right ideology and pro-environmental attitudes and actions (Li et al., 2018; Cichocki et al., 2024; Lundquist, 2025). These differences are likely to emerge for intra-group analysis or based on other country group configurations, but as we show in Table 10, did not showcase relevant inter-group differences for the low, medium and high-environmental impact country groups selected.

In general, none of the variables below yielded a Crámer’s V of 0.3 or above for any of the three analytical steps undertaken. This shows that any statistical difference amongst groups is moderately significant at best. Nevertheless, there are some interesting numerical highlights we will delve on in the discussion section.

Although not statistically significant, the variable “Protecting the environment versus economic growth and job creation” deserves separate attention given its relevance to sustainability debates. Table 11 presents the percentage of respondents in each country who prioritized environmental protection over economic growth, grouped according to the low, mid and high-impact classification.

Table 10
Sustainability-related variables that did not yield statistically-significant differences amongst low, mid, and high-impact groups.

Variable (Crámer’s V ≤ 0.3 for all three analysis, where: Analysis 1: only SDI countries in the low-impact group; Analysis 2: GFN + SDI countries in the low-impact group; Analysis 3: only GFN countries in the low-impact group)		Results for the three groups		
		Low-impact (SDI/GFN + SDI/GFN)	Medium-impact	High-impact
Feeling of happiness	% of respondents indicating they feel very happy	38.5 %/35.7 %/36.0 %	22.1 %	29.0 %
	% of respondents indicating they feel quite happy	44.1 %/48.6 %/50.9 %	62.8 %	61.3 %
	% of respondents indicating they feel very happy or quite happy	82.6 %/84.3 %/86.9 %	84.9 %	90.3 %
State of health (subjective)	% of respondents indicating they feel very healthy or fairly healthy	58.7 %/60.9 %/64.6 %	66.8 %	73.0 %
	How much freedom of choice and control	% of respondents indicating 8 out of 10 being 0 none at all and 10 a great deal of freedom of choice and control	16.2 %/16.6 %/17.2 %	22.6 %
Member: Belong to conservation, the environment, ecology, animal rights group	% of respondents indicating 9 out of 10 being 0 none at all and 10 a great deal of freedom of choice and control	8.4 %/8.3 %/8.1 %	9.1 %	13.1 %
	% of respondents indicating 10 out of 10 being 0 none at all and 10 a great deal of freedom of choice and control	28.4 %/26.7 %/25.4 %	13.8 %	12.2 %
Confidence: The Environmental Protection Movement	% of respondents mentioning membership	14.2 %/15.9 %/17.4 %	4.9 %	13.2 %
	% of respondents indicating a great deal of trust	16.4 %/19.0 %/22.2 %	9.3 %	9.1 %
Confidence: The United Nations	% of respondents indicating quite a lot of trust	35.4 %/37.4 %/40.7 %	46.8 %	51.2 %
	% of respondents indicating a great deal or quite a lot of trust	48.4 %/48.3 %/47.7 %	47.9 %	58.3 %
Self positioning in political scale	% of respondents self positioning as left-winged (1, 2, or 3 in a 1–10 scale, where 1 is left and 10 is right)	16.9 %/15.6 %/13.7 %	21.4 %	22.0 %
	% of respondents self positioning themselves as right-winged (8, 9, or 10 in a 1–10 scale, where 1 is left and 10 is right)	29.4 %/32.0 %/34.6 %	16.6 %	16.4 %
How close you feel: World	% of respondents feeling very close or close	38.9 %/49.9 %/61.8 %	57.2 %	47.8 %
	Protecting environment vs. Economic growth	% of respondents choosing protecting the environment over economic growth	61.9 %/60.4 %/58.2 %	60.7 %

Caption for Table 10. Sustainability-related variables that did not yield statistically significant differences among low-, medium-, and high-impact country groups. Variables included did not meet the threshold of Cramér’s $V \geq 0.3$ across three analyses: (1) only SDI countries in the low-impact group, (2) GFN + SDI countries in the low-impact group, and (3) only GFN countries in the low-impact group.

Table 11
Preference for protecting the environment over economic growth and job creation across country groups.

Country	Protecting environment is more important than economic growth and creating jobs (% of overall responses that choose protecting the environment)	Group based on Global Footprint Network and Sustainable Development Index Databases
Egypt	31.7	Low-impact
Tunisia	33.1	Low-impact
Jordan	47.5	Low-impact
Albania	49.2	Low-impact
Netherlands	50.0	High-impact
United States	50.4	High-impact
France	50.5	Mid-impact
Chile	51.5	Mid-impact
Greece	52.0	Mid-impact
Thailand	52.7	Low-impact
Croatia	52.8	Mid-impact
Austria	53.5	High-impact
Ecuador	55.3	Low-impact
Singapore	55.8	High-impact
Portugal	57.1	Mid-impact
Peru	57.2	Low-impact
South Korea	57.4	High-impact
Spain	57.5	Mid-impact
Italy	59.8	Mid-impact
Canada	60.0	High-impact
Uruguay	64.9	Low-impact
Denmark	65.4	High-impact
Australia	66.2	High-impact
Philippines	66.3	Low-impact
Norway	67.1	High-impact
Georgia	67.7	Low-impact
Colombia	69.2	Low-impact
Iceland	71.2	High-impact
Indonesia	72.1	Low-impact

Caption for Table 11. Preference for environmental protection over economic growth and job creation in low-, medium-, and high-impact countries. Percentages indicate the share of respondents prioritizing the environment (N = 50,432, EVS/WVS, 2017–2022). Grouping is based on the Global Footprint Network (GFN) and Sustainable Development Index (SDI) classification (low-impact: white; mid-impact: light grey; high-impact: dark grey).

Results show wide variation across groups, with both low and high-impact countries represented at the lower and higher ends of the spectrum, highlighting the gap between stated preferences and actual environmental outcomes.

3.5. Consideration of other relevant factors: multidimensional poverty index and average temperatures at national level

3.5.1. Multidimensional Poverty Index

Low environmental impact is often associated with poverty and the deprivation of basic needs. Although all countries selected for this analysis have a high or very high Human Development Index (HDI), it was important to further verify that they also score very low in the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), to ensure that their sustainability outcomes are not merely the result of structural deprivation (Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative, 2018). In particular, multidimensional poverty may play a role in shaping sustainability indicators, especially when low per capita environmental impact is primarily the result of limited access to resources, rather than deliberate

Table 12
Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) indicators for low-impact countries.

Country	Vulnerable to poverty	In severe poverty	Rank (out of 105)
	% Population	% Population	
Thailand	7,23	0,13	8
Jordan	0,95	0,09	11
Tunisia	3,75	0,19	12
Albania	7,30	0,16	16
Ecuador	7,55	0,83	28
Egypt	6,08	0,58	32
Colombia	6,18	0,90	34
Indonesia	9,10	1,24	38
Philippines	9,33	4,74	40
Peru	12,46	2,72	44

Caption for Table 12. Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) indicators for low-impact countries included in the statistical analysis. Despite all countries having a high or very high Human Development Index (HDI), the MPI was used to verify that low environmental impact was not primarily the result of structural deprivation. The table presents the percentage of the population vulnerable to poverty, the percentage in severe poverty, and each country’s MPI rank out of 105 countries (Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative, 2018). No data was available for Uruguay or Georgia.

policy choices or cultural values. Since the Human Development Index used in both the Global Footprint Network (GFN) and Sustainable Development Index (SDI) databases may not fully capture this complexity, the MPI provides an important complementary lens.

The latest MPI data, calculated by the United Nations for 105 countries in 2018, was therefore used to cross-check the selected sustainable countries included in the statistical analysis. These countries had the following MPI indicators:

As shown in the analysis, countries in the low-impact group are relatively consistent with low levels of poverty as measured by the MPI, with an average of 6.99 % of the population vulnerable to poverty and 1.16 % in severe poverty across the countries listed. Additional research needs to be undertaken to understand the relationship between multidimensional poverty and aggregated sustainability at country level, but rankings across datasets (MPI, GFN and SDI) are consistent.

3.5.2. Average temperatures

Another factor that should be taken into account regarding results of the analysis are average temperatures, as extreme weather has been proven to increase reliance on fossil fuels (Zhao et al., 2023), and could explain why colder countries are more polluting. An analysis of the selected countries regarding the 10 year average of temperatures yielded that, effectively, there is a correlation between average temperatures and consumption per capita as can be seen in the following table:

Further study is needed to account for temperature-related differences, as these appear relevant but do not fully explain levels of consumption. For example, Georgia and Albania are at the lower end of the spectrum in terms of average temperatures and both have an HDI of 0.8, close to Greece, Italy, and Portugal, which have HDIs of 0.89, 0.89, and 0.87 respectively. Yet, despite their lower average temperatures, Georgia and Albania manage to maintain significantly lower levels of ecological footprint of consumption per capita (EFConsPC).

Likewise, Norway’s EFConsPC of 5.4 with an average temperature of 2.6 °C is significantly lower than Austria’s 5.76 or Denmark’s 7.17, despite their considerably higher average temperatures of 8.1 °C and 9.4 °C respectively. This suggests that discounting environmental hardship –such as extreme cold or extreme heat– from sustainability indicators could provide an interesting line of analysis and add further nuance to sustainable country selection.

Table 13
Average temperatures and ecological footprint per capita in selected countries.

Country	Temperature 10 year average for 2014–2024 (°C)	Ecological footprint of consumption per capita	Group
Canada	−3.8	7.38	High-impact
Iceland	2.1	22.55	High-impact
Norway	2.7	5.4	High-impact
Austria	8.3	5.76	High-impact
Denmark	9.6	7.17	High-impact
Chile	9.7	3.86	Mid-impact
Georgia	9.9	2.58	Low-impact
United States	10.1	7.44	High-impact
Netherlands	11.3	6.2	High-impact
France	12.4	4.4	Mid-impact
Croatia	12.9	3.79	Mid-impact
South Korea	12.8	5.82	High-impact
Albania	13.3	2.09	Low-impact
Italy	14.0	4.02	Mid-impact
Spain	14.7	3.98	Mid-impact
Greece	15.2	3.72	Mid-impact
Portugal	16.5	3.77	Mid-impact
Uruguay	18.3	2.19	Low-impact
Peru	19.9	2.28	Low-impact
Jordan	20.0	1.35	Low-impact
Tunisia	20.8	1.38	Low-impact
Ecuador	21.8	1.71	Low-impact
Australia	22.4	5.77	High-impact
Egypt	23.6	1.45	Low-impact
Colombia	25.3	2.01	Low-impact
Indonesia	26.1	1.59	Low-impact
Philippines	26.6	1.2	Low-impact
Thailand	27.2	2.35	Low-impact
Singapore	28.1	5.88	High-impact

Caption for Table 13. Average temperatures and ecological footprint per capita in selected countries. The table compares the 10-year average national temperatures from 2014 to 2024 with the ecological footprint of consumption per capita across selected countries grouped for the low, mid and high-impact (low-impact: white; mid-impact: light grey; high-impact: dark grey). Results suggest a correlation between colder climates and higher per capita ecological footprints, pointing towards the energy demands of heating, although notable exceptions exist. Source: [Worlddeconomics.com](https://www.worlddeconomics.com) available at <https://www.worlddeconomics.com/Indicator-Data/ESG/Environment/Temperatures/> for average temperatures and GFN 2022 for ecological footprint of consumption per capita.

4. Discussion and implications for environmental education

4.1. Religion, spirituality and community

The integrated analysis highlights that religion, spirituality, and community related variables associate with sustainability outcomes across country groups. Religious denomination, importance of God, household size and intergenerational responsibility associated strongly with the classification into low-, medium-, and high-impact countries. Respondents in the low-impact group showed higher levels of religious belonging and spirituality, often coupled with larger, intergenerational household structures.

By contrast, high-impact countries displayed higher levels of secularization, smaller household sizes, and greater emphasis on self-expression values. While these societies are often associated with social progress and individual freedoms, the analysis suggests that secular-rational orientations appear alongside higher ecological footprints. Inglehart and Welzel's cultural map situates these countries within the secular-rational/self-expression quadrant, while low-impact countries cluster closer to traditional and survival-oriented orientations, reinforcing the observed link between spiritual and communal worldviews and lower environmental impact. Additionally, non-denominational spirituality seems to be at play across contexts, and further study is needed to understand the link between non-denominational spirituality and sustainable values.

For environmental education (EE), these findings suggest that, despite the fact that high levels of denominational religion is not an assurance of low environmental impact (e.g. the United States or Singapore have religiosity numbers similar to those displayed in the SDI low-impact country group), community-based moral and spiritual orientations may provide important resources for sustainability. Three implications stand out:

- **Plurality of worldviews:** EE should engage both secular and spiritual frameworks, recognizing that values rooted in certain forms of religion and spirituality –whether denominational or not– could be motivators of sustainable practices. This has already been pointed out by various authors ([Morrison et al., 2015](#); [Marshall, 2016](#); [Puglisi and Buitendag, 2022](#)) who argue for more culturally-relevant environmental policy that puts into value religious, spiritual and ancestral traditions in sustainability and conservation policy.
- **Relational ethics and community structures:** Traditions that emphasize reciprocity, care, and intergenerational duty appear linked to more sustainable outcomes. Strengthening these relational values in EE could inform EE approaches aiming to enhance learners' sense of shared responsibility beyond individual choice. Larger, interdependent households and community ties appear associated with lower environmental impact, suggesting that EE initiatives should not only target individual behaviour but could also build on community practices of care, trust, and mutual support.

Rather than viewing religion and spirituality as residual or marginal in environmental education, it might be effective to treat them as ontological and ethical resources that shape how people critically and meaningfully understand their place in the world, and their responsibilities within it, including their relationship and ties to family, community, tradition, biodiversity and ecosystems. Incorporating this framework could be a way to both reinforce religious and spiritual efforts towards sustainability, as well as a way to bridge the gap with anthropogenic scepticism amongst religious populations. However,

religion and spirituality, despite being the majority belief system¹ and a key relational framework to understand how the human and the non-human interact, is not generally addressed or integrated in mainstream environmental education policy.

4.2. Integrating spiritual and relational dimensions into environmental education policy and practice

Key sustainability competence frameworks such as the *Education for Sustainable Development Goals Learning Objectives* (UNESCO, 2017) and the *GreenComp: The European sustainability competence framework* (Bianchi et al., 2022) do not mention religion or spirituality at all.² These frameworks highlight the importance of family, community, and a critical understanding of human stewardship of the web of life, but such aims can hardly be pursued meaningfully without considering spirituality and religiosity in communities where these constitute relevant markers of attitudes, values and actions, both individually and collectively. Additionally, sustainability competences related to valuing Indigenous knowledge systems, heritage and community-building could benefit from a stronger weaving together of secular-scientific knowledge with non-secular knowledge traditions.

Critical pedagogies, place-based pedagogies and transdisciplinary approaches (Freire, 1970; Noguera de Echeverri, 2004; Gruenewald, 2008; Ludwig et al., 2024), which root learning in lived experience and dialogue, provide an appropriate framework to integrate these resources across diverse ontological and epistemological backgrounds. By acknowledging the spiritual, moral, and communal dimensions of sustainability, environmental education can move beyond purely cognitive approaches and foster deeper engagement with the values that sustain environmental responsibility. After all, there is “no dichotomy between the technical and the cultural” in education (Freire, 1984, p. 62).

To translate these insights into practice, environmental education needs concrete mechanisms to bring relational and spiritual dimensions into teaching and learning without essentialising belief systems or privileging any particular tradition. Three complementary steps can support this operational shift. First, sustainability competence frameworks could be revised to ensure that religion and spirituality are neither downplayed nor overstated, but recognised as potential sources of meaning, motivation, and ethical reasoning where appropriate. Second, tools are needed to contextualise competence frameworks so that religious and spiritual orientations in each setting can be engaged constructively, helping learners make sense of scientific knowledge in environmental education while also strengthening local cultural practices that support sustainability. Third, educational activities, resources, and programmes can be designed and implemented across educational levels (from early childhood to adult and lifelong learning), stakeholder groups (students, teachers, policymakers, researchers, SME and NGO practitioners, and others), and learning spaces (formal, non-formal, and informal education). Identifying and drawing on local initiatives that already weave beliefs, heritage, and cultural practices into environmental learning can offer valuable inspiration for programme design. Approaches such as *The Work That Reconnects* (Macy and Young Brown, 2014), the head–hands–heart eco-literacy model (Singleton, 2015), popular education traditions in rural development (Freire, 1984), and heritage-based and arts-based methodologies such as *Theatre of the Oppressed* (Boal, 1998, 2013) illustrate how different traditions have long fostered relational, ethical, and place-rooted engagement. These

¹ Belief in God averages 74.6 % among all respondents in the EVS/WVS. The most atheist countries in the survey are China (16.9 %), Sweden (34.4 %), and South Korea (40.6 %). In all other countries, approximately half or more of the population identify as believers in God.

² The term belief/beliefs is mentioned once in the UNESCO report and four times in the GreenComp, but mostly referring to belief systems more generally, not religion and spirituality in particular.

examples point to a wide repertoire from which educators can draw. Whatever the case, the concrete expression of pedagogical activities will necessarily differ by context in order to remain responsive to group age, size, and cultural needs. Together, these steps can help environmental education harness diverse ethical and worldview resources, grounding sustainability learning in cultural meaning-making while reinforcing scientific knowledge, fostering critical engagement with evidence, and avoiding disengagement from the scientific foundations of environmental education.

4.3. Insularity

The analysis suggests that insularity may play a role in shaping sustainability outcomes, though its relevance varies by dataset. Islands are disproportionately represented in the low-impact group according to the Global Footprint Network (GFN), but this trend does not hold under the Sustainable Development Index (SDI). This divergence points both to methodological differences between indicators and to the complexity of interpreting geographic factors.

Island nations often face structural constraints –limited land, reliance on imports, and high vulnerability to climate change– that can encourage efficiency, frugality, and community-based adaptation (Baldacchino, 2006; Niles and Baldacchino, 2011). At the same time, dependence on external trade and tourism may generate pressures that offset these advantages. The key insight for environmental education (EE) is that territorial conditions and resource constraints can foster sustainability independently of individual awareness or values.

Importantly, many of the values and practices observed in island societies –such as strong community interdependence, resource circularity, and resilience-building– may be transferable to non-island contexts. EE can play a role in exporting these lessons, showing how strategies rooted in constraint and vulnerability can inform more sustainable ways of living globally. This requires a pedagogical approach that not only acknowledges geographic particularities but also identifies the broader cultural resources they offer for sustainability.

4.4. Happiness, freedom and health

The analysis of subjective well-being indicators –happiness, freedom of choice, and perceived health– did not reveal statistically significant differences across low-, medium, and high-impact groups. Levels of self-reported happiness were high in all contexts, with over 80 % of respondents in each group describing themselves as either very happy or quite happy. Similarly, indicators of perceived health and freedom of choice showed broadly comparable distributions, with only modest variations. These results suggest that subjective well-being is not strongly associated with environmental impact when comparing countries of high and very high human development. This reinforces evidence from the literature that subjective well-being tends to plateau once basic material needs are met, and that beyond this threshold, additional consumption does not significantly increase happiness or life satisfaction (Easterlin, 1973; Helliwell et al., 2012).

For environmental education (EE), these findings carry two important implications. First, they suggest that appeals to happiness or quality of life may not suffice as differentiators of sustainable societies, since well-being is widely reported across contexts regardless of ecological footprint. Second, EE could emphasize that sustainable pathways do not imply a sacrifice in happiness, freedom, or health. Highlighting that lower-impact societies report levels of subjective well-being comparable to or higher than those of high-impact societies may help counter narratives that equate sustainability with deprivation.

Ultimately, integrating well-being into EE means moving beyond framing sustainability as a constraint on freedoms, and instead presenting it as compatible with –and potentially reinforcing of– human prosperity. This requires pedagogical strategies that connect environmental responsibility to lived experiences of satisfaction, agency, and

health, and critically addressing the role and types of consumption in life satisfaction.

4.5. Protecting the environment versus economic growth

When asked whether protecting the environment is more important than economic growth and job creation, results across country groups revealed no clear alignment with sustainability outcomes. While some low-impact countries scored relatively low (e.g., Egypt 31.7 %, Tunisia 33.1 %), others such as Indonesia (72.1 %), Colombia (69.2 %), and Georgia (67.7 %) scored among the highest. Conversely, high-impact countries such as Norway (67.1 %), Iceland (71.2 %), and Australia (66.2 %) also displayed strong pro-environment responses. Mid-impact countries, including Italy (59.8 %) and Spain (57.5 %), fell in the mid-range.

This distribution indicates that declared preference for environmental protection over growth is not a reliable predictor of actual environmental performance. Both low-impact and high-impact countries appear across the full spectrum of responses, suggesting a disconnect between stated values and measured environmental outcomes at country level. These findings echo broader research showing that environmental attitudes do not necessarily translate into sustainable behaviours, and that these do not necessarily achieve aggregated reduction in environmental impact (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002; Li et al., 2018; Vlăsceanu et al., 2024).

For environmental education (EE), this has several important implications. First, it calls for caution in over-relying on attitudinal indicators as proxies for sustainability. While valuable, survey responses may reflect cultural norms, social desirability, or political discourse rather than consistent behavioural patterns. For example, according to the Reuters Report (2020), Norway reports relatively low levels of concern about anthropogenic climate change, yet displays strong pro-environmental values in the World Values Survey data. Future research examining within-country differences and specific cross-country comparisons attending to cultural, historical, media-related, and geopolitical specificities could shed further light on this phenomenon.

Second, it highlights the need for pedagogical approaches that move beyond raising awareness of the environment versus growth trade-off and toward cultivating the competences and structural conditions that enable people to act on these preferences. To support EE policy and programme design, structured indicators are required that distinguish and examine the links between individual and collective pro-environmental beliefs, attitudes, behaviours, actions and aggregated impacts. Finally, EE could draw on regenerative approaches, which propose transcending the nature-economy dualism to demonstrate that environmental care, economic vitality, and wellbeing can go hand in hand (Escobar, 2011; Wahl, 2016).

4.6. The cases of Georgia and Albania

The cases of Georgia and Albania are particularly noteworthy, as both are relatively cold countries with high levels of human development and significantly low ecological footprints. Religiosity is also high: 73.1 % of respondents in Albania reported that religion is very or rather important in their lives, while in Georgia this figure rises to 94.7 %. When asked to choose between protecting the environment and pursuing economic growth, 49.2 % of respondents in Albania and 67.7 % in Georgia prioritized environmental protection.

Further research is needed to better understand the relationship between belief systems, environmental awareness, technological advancement, and human well-being in these two countries, as this could provide important insights and possible avenues of innovation for other European regions.

4.7. Environmental and sustainability indicators

The analysis highlights the need for more nuanced cross-country research on the relationship between values and sustainability indicators. While values appear to be important correlates of environmental outcomes, the results show that they do not always align in coherent or predictable ways. For instance, countries with high levels of pro-environment attitudes are not necessarily those with lower ecological footprints, and conversely, countries with relatively modest attitudinal support sometimes perform better in sustainability terms. This lack of association and/or correlation suggests that, despite decades long requests for improvement in sustainability metrics, current approaches to measuring sustainability-related values may still be too scarce, too narrow or insufficiently contextualized (Wilson et al., 2007; Brulé, 2022; Radácsi and Szigeti, 2024).

For environmental education (EE), this underlines the importance of developing sustainability indicators that are sensitive to cultural diversity, contextual variation, and structural constraints. Without such nuance, indicators risk oversimplifying complex relationships between belief, behaviour, and environmental impact. Advancing this area of research is critical not only for academic understanding but also for designing EE frameworks that genuinely foster sustainability comprehensively.

5. Limitations of the study

This study is subject to several limitations that should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings.

First, the classification of countries into low-, medium-, and high-impact categories relies on threshold choices that, while grounded in widely used sustainability indicators, may influence the results. Future research could complement this approach by applying alternative cut-off points and conducting robustness checks to assess whether the associations observed here remain stable across different grouping criteria. While both datasets are widely used, their methodological differences affect which countries fall into each group. Consequently, some of the observed patterns may reflect dataset construction rather than substantive differences in sustainability outcomes. Moreover, conducting a systematic literature review of “sustainable” countries across diverse sustainability databases and indexes –which, to the best of our knowledge, has not yet been undertaken– and repeating the integrated analysis with alternative country groupings, while also accounting for temporal trends, would further strengthen the reliability of the findings.

Second, integrating sustainability indicators with the Joint European Values Survey/World Values Survey (EVS/WVS) introduces further constraints. The analysis is limited to countries that appear in both datasets, which reduces global representativeness and may bias findings toward regions with stronger survey infrastructure and funding. Moreover, the EVS/WVS primarily relies on face-to-face interviewing in many contexts, which can introduce interviewer effects and social desirability bias in responses to value-laden questions (World Values Survey Association, Fieldwork Sampling Guidelines; Weighting Guidelines). Cross-national surveys are also sensitive to cultural and linguistic variation in how respondents interpret concepts related to religion, family, trust, or environmental attitudes, which may complicate direct comparisons across societies. These factors may contribute to differences observed across country groups, particularly on sensitive topics such as spirituality, trust, or intergenerational responsibility, where cultural response styles and social norms are salient. While these constraints do not undermine the general patterns identified, future research could triangulate EVS/WVS data with alternative cross-cultural datasets and qualitative or mixed-methods approaches to further validate and deepen the interpretation of value orientations in relation to sustainability outcomes.

Third, while Cramér’s V was used to identify statistically significant associations across groups, this approach is limited to categorical

variables and does not account for interactions, confounding factors, or causal relationships. Associations identified here should therefore be interpreted as indicative rather than explanatory.

Fourth, additional contextual factors such as historical trajectories, political institutions, economic models, and environmental vulnerabilities were not systematically included in the analysis. Variables such as poverty and average temperatures were examined as complementary indicators, but these do not exhaust the range of structural conditions that shape sustainability outcomes.

Fifth, this study relies on cross-sectional data, which allows the identification of associations between values and environmental impact but does not permit causal inference. The findings therefore point to correlational patterns rather than causal pathways linking cultural orientations and sustainability outcomes. Future research could strengthen causal understanding by combining longitudinal designs with mixed-methods approaches, including qualitative case studies and participatory or ethnographic research, to explore how values and worldviews translate into sustainability practices over time and across contexts.

Sixth, a temporal consideration also applies to the integration of datasets. The SDI and GFN indicators are derived from recent environmental and development data cycles, while the EVS/WVS analysis is based on Wave 7 fieldwork. Although these sources do not align perfectly in time, they overlap within a recent period in which both sustainability indicators and cultural values are generally stable, as value orientations tend to evolve gradually across generations rather than fluctuating sharply year-to-year, and sustainability performance indicators also move slowly for high-HDI countries. For these reasons, temporal differences are unlikely to meaningfully distort the associations observed. Nevertheless, future research could benefit from fully synchronised longitudinal data and dynamic modelling to examine whether changes in cultural orientations precede or follow sustainability performance shifts over time.

Finally, cross-country cultural maps such as the Inglehart–Welzel framework provide useful heuristics but also risk oversimplification by clustering diverse societies into broad categories. This limits their explanatory power for environmental sustainability, which may be better understood through more fine-grained, context-specific approaches.

Despite these limitations, the study provides an integrative framework that connects sustainability indicators with value-based data. Future research can build on this foundation by refining cross-country, as well as regional value indicators, expanding contextual variables, and applying mixed-methods approaches to capture the nuanced interplay between values, beliefs, and sustainability outcomes.

6. Conclusions

This study set out to explore whether countries with high human development and low environmental impact share values, and how such insights might help rethink the foundations of environmental education (EE). By integrating sustainability indicators with cross-national value data, the analysis demonstrates that cultural and moral orientations—particularly those linked to religion, spirituality, and community—associate strongly with differences in environmental impact. Countries classified as low-impact showed higher levels of religiosity, intergenerational responsibility, and communal living arrangements, in contrast to the smaller, more secular household structures typical of high-impact societies. These findings suggest that spiritual and relational worldviews, often overlooked in current EE frameworks, may constitute important resources for sustainability.

Nevertheless, while this study identifies consistent associations between value orientations and environmental impact patterns, these should not be interpreted as causal pathways. The analysis is cross-sectional and correlational; future research using longitudinal and mixed-methods designs is needed to explore mechanisms and directionality.

At the same time, the study highlights the limits of relying solely on attitudinal indicators such as pro-environmental preferences or subjective well-being, which did not consistently differentiate between impact groups. This underlines the importance of developing more nuanced, context-sensitive approaches to measuring sustainability-related values and competences. Insularity, poverty levels, and climatic conditions further illustrate how structural factors shape sustainability outcomes, sometimes more decisively than individual attitudes.

The implications for EE are significant. Existing competence frameworks such as UNESCO's ESD Learning Objectives and the EU's Green-Comp emphasize values of responsibility, justice, and community, but they refrain from incorporating religion and spirituality, despite these being dominant belief frameworks in much of the world. Our findings suggest that weaving spiritual, moral, and relational dimensions into EE can enrich its cultural relevance, strengthen learners' sense of reciprocity and shared responsibility, increase the relevance of scientific knowledge across contexts and move education beyond narrowly cognitive or behavioural models.

Ultimately, if EE is to foster the transformative competences needed for sustainability, it must recognize the plurality of worldviews that underpin human–environment relations. This means treating spirituality, religiosity, and community ethics not as residual or marginal, but as integral to how people make meaning, care for one another, and act upon the world. By doing so, EE can become better attuned to the lived values and experiences that sustain environmental stewardship and collective action in the face of planetary crisis.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ana Fernández-Aballí Altamirano: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Carlos Fernández-Aballí Altamirano:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Link to the data has been shared upon submission of manuscript.

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